

**EFFECT OF FOREIGN FASHION ON STUDENTS DRESSING IN
NIGERIAN UNIVERSITIES: TOWARDS A CULTURAL
SYNCHRONIZATION**

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Abstract

The paper examines the effect of foreign fashion on students dressing in Nigerian universities, for being fashionable and remains trending. Fashion expresses personal beauty, style, and glamour with which culture is examined with goodness and change within specific time limit and is constant only for minutes; as a social phenomenon. Although centuries back fashion was an elite thing which, globalization of fashion is fast eroding among non-western cultures such as Africa, especially those of Nigeria. The paper employs both primary and secondary sources of data collection to quarry the nature and effect of foreign fashion on students in Nigerian universities as the targeted population. Relying on the findings of the paper indicates that students preferred foreign fashion to indigenous fashion and the desire to attract the male counterpart, academic grade and favor motivated students to dress in seductive manner that has significant effect on students dressing pattern and conclude that dress code be enforced while dress style should be monitored in congruent with indigenous fashion. This is to reinvigorate the drive to regularly broadcast in institutional media to promote indigenous fashion in Nigerian university system as a way of forestalling this hydra-headed menace invading the holy of holies of the African cultural development and education of the African reality.

Keywords: *Foreign Fashion, Indigenous Fashion, Students, Dress, Nigeria, Universities, effect.*

I. Introduction

Fashion often is a reflection of the society. Fashion however is a popular style or practice, especially clothing, footwear, accessories, makeups, (Wikipedia, 2022), among others. Thus, fashion refers to a distinctive and often habitual trend in style with which a person dresses as well as to prevailing styles in behavior. Adding that the transformation of fashion is gradual and not revolutionary in approach, but it is a continuous process of change. Hence, fashion is dynamic, learned, acquired, as well as transmitted through contact or means of communication flow from one generation to another. The Nigerian fashion is observed to be waning or fading out as a result of the acceptance and adaptation of foreign fashion is a function of the competitive and innovative of the fashion industry is, it actually has to follow what becomes the “Fashion Cycle”, which has no specific

measurable time frame. Some styles sustain for longer period of time while some die out soon, and some styles come back years after they disappeared (Abbasi, 2013:117). This is that fashion changes with time and has always been evolving to fit the taste, lifestyle and demands of society of all ages across the globe.

It is therefore only natural that the new trends are introduced to the public gradually. The introduction stage is the beginning of an exciting roller coaster ride that the Fashion trends go through every season. There is no doubt that every individual has a unique taste, but it seems that when style is worn so many people around us, it is only natural that you will find yourself following the trends and want to try to be fashionable as well. There are however certain rules when it comes to fashion, especially classic styles that trend for a period while fad fashion comes quickly and is accepted by the masses very rapidly, sweeps away and become less desirable in short time. It is short lived. But classic styles are long lasting. It, therefore, the level of “empathy” that the citizens of less developing societies to empathize with taste for modern transformation of such societies to be possible.

This is as Nwosu (2010), opines that the access to foreign fashion is linked to individual modernity. The acceptance of foreign fashion by the Nigerian students as well as the society cannot be over flogged. Foreign fashion, Olori (2003) notes, is a trend in clothing that is invented by the western developed nations fashionable dresses that has eroded the cultural practices of the African life styles that is built on modesty and decency in dress patterns. Although there are no universally acceptable way or ways as far as dressing is concern. But as Olori (2003) emphasized that dresses are meant to serve some definite or definable purposes, the country or region notwithstanding. This is saying that dresses are part of a people’s culture and they define their tribal or ethnic identity, and climatic conditions, among others.

Besides, dress being a means for cultural identity, they has ornamental or aesthetic purpose for protection of the body against harsh weather conditions especially for covering the intimate parts of the body (answer.com, 2011; article base.com, 2011). These purposes of dressing are very important as they constitute major aspects of a person’s personality. But as important as these purposes of dressing are, they are fading away as a result of the influx of foreign fashions in Nigeria. The dressing pattern of university students are as a result of foreign fashion invasion on the indigenous wears in manner that does not show decency and responsibility of the African personality traits. This is because indigenous fashion and pursuit has also been abandoned by the youths to seductive foreign fashionable that spreads indecent dressing and immorality to Nigeria’s social fabric (Nigerian films.com, 2009 as cited in Mac-Moses, 2015:3).

Empirical studies have shown that there is a correlation between foreign fashion and indecent dressing among youths for instance, despite rules were made to mitigate improper dressing, to cover intimate parts of the body and must not expose the breast, stomach, and bare chest. But on the campuses of these universities in Nigeria students still dress indecently as a result of foreign fashion and its influence on the generality youths is not desirable. It is increasingly becoming obvious that foreign fashion has gradually replaced indigenous Nigerian fashion and thus taken over the dressing pattern of students in Nigeria’s university space. Egwim (2010) noted that, the indecent dressing among students in Nigerian tertiary institutions have assumed a new dimension as a result of

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foreign fashion. The effect of foreign fashion on students dressing therefore need to be interrogated to understand the trends and effect of this inevitable change arising from foreign fashion.

II. Statement of the Problem

There is an old adage “nothing is permanent” is a common usage that best suited the discourse of the average Nigerian students who are always eager to dress in foreign fashions. They see foreign fashions as a model that is better than indigenous fashions; many students tend to imitate the foreign fashion and culture in terms of dressing. This have often resulted into indecent dressing among university students. The way students dresses, especially the females, dresses seductively leave much to be desired. Such dresses they wear is just an inch longer than their pants, a situation they struggle to sit down, find difficulty in climbing motorcycles, cross gutters as well as pick anything on the ground. Aside the skimpy nature of these foreign fashions, they are transparent, exposing certain parts of the body that under normal dressing pattern ought to be covered from the glare of people. Conversely, their male counterpart students always dresses dirty with dirty jeans having multiple pockets with holes deliberately created around kneel and lower part of the trousers. Therefore, consequences of rape, sexual harassment, cultism, ritualism and immorality among other vices is also simplify among students. The implication is that foreign fashion can hinder the moral behavior of the students if not checked, it can lead to total destruction of the indigenous fashion and thus endanger the decency and modesty of the indigenous Nigerian fashion need be interrogated.

III. Conceptual Analysis

Fashion is as old as humankind. People always used one thing or the other to adorn themselves. Maryam (2012) figured fashion as the style of clothing worn by most people of a particular country. Therefore, fashion as it related to clothing is what is in style at a particular time. Wikipedia (2022) contemplates fashion as a popular style or practice especially in clothing, footwear, accessories, makeup body piercing among others. The concept of fashion highlights the process of style change over time, for instance, a style of clothing is introduced as fashion, but its use over time becomes a custom, handed from one generation to another (Egbanabo, 2008). Broadly, fashion is viewed as a chronology of changing forms and a critique of wider cultural influences and their historical interpretation of communicating with others.

Primarily, the history of fashion reveals the importance of changes in appearance, but also the way fashion is conceived, who participates, and for what and how many occasions (Ahuja, 2021:93). It highlights that fashion means different thing to different people. This is because fashion is a distinctive and often habited trend in the style individuals dresses to prevailing styles in behavior. Fashion also refers to the newest creation of textile designers (Wikipedia, 2022). Fashion is a certain way chosen and that becomes defined by people as a large number of them utilizes that particular style has appeal to an already occurring set of beliefs that style becomes fashion. In the light of this, Ted (2013) subscribed that fashion can be described as adornment of which there are double sides such as fashion and anti-fashion through the capitalization of clothing accessories and shoes, what once constituted anti-fashion becomes part of fashion as the

lines between fashion and anti-fashion are blurred. This is so as anti-fashion is fixed and changes little over time, but fashion changes very quickly and spread demographically throughout the world wherever people can communicate easily with each other. As Maryam (2015 as cited in Mac-Moses, 2015:10) emphasized that anti-fashion is a situation of fixed while fashion is concerned with social phenomenon. Adding further she asserted anti-fashion are clothes worn by natural rulers such as kings does not change over time.

While foreign fashion entails wearing of foreign clothing which is exclusively a human characteristic and is a feature of most human societies, as a result of the economic principles of interdependence and materialism. Basically, foreign fashions are western styles of clothing, accessories and makeup worn by people. This is as the historians Laver and Braudel (2013) noted, the beginning of foreign fashion could be traced to the French, Italian and Britain, and that the western styles of clothing started about the middle of the 14th century. The summary truth is that foreign fashion as it relates to clothing has undergone dramatic changes. Wikipedia (2022) opines that the most dramatic change in early western fashion was a sudden drastic shortening and tightening of the female overgarment from half-length barely covering the buttocks.

Accordingly, this created the distinctive western outlines of a tailored top worn over leggings or trousers (Mac-Moses, 2015:11), the pace of change and acceleration in fashion brought about the dressing and spread to other non-western regions. The changes in fashion brought about serious fragmentation among the major fashion capitals of New York, London, Paris and Milan, which are hosts to the biggest fashion companies and renowned for their great influence on global fashion (Morgan, 2013). Arising from globalization, foreign fashions such as clothing have spread rapidly to several countries, especially Nigeria where western fashion has flooded it with a sweeping change, generating ideas and images, in their quests for modernity (Mac-Moses, 2015:12).

James (2014) noted that whereas foreign fashions such as clothing had previously been targeted as wealth, elite, gender, age and occupation, the taste and preferences of young people now became a significant aspect of the march of fashionable dresses, which appears to be cheap and affordable to individuals than local fashion (Brain, 2007). Empirical studies such as Ukpebor (2010) and Ipogah (2011) opines that there is gradual influence on the clothing styles along the coastal communities which came about with the arrival of foreign merchants and travelers through the commercial activities of European clothes. These fashionable dresses include jeans, suits, and high-heel shoes, skimpy and skinny shirts for women and so on. However, developing countries have copied the foreign or westernized dresses for their conscious young people who want to be at speed with fashion trends and yet lacked effective purchasing capacity. Foreign fashion as can be seen is one of the instruments of imperialism used by the West to exploit the indigenous fashion and culture. This is that the high rate of importation of foreign clothes that does not appeal to the cultural heritage of the African personality is dangerous in promoting moral behavior as well as decent dressing among students of Nigerian universities.

IV. Theoretical Framework

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The anchor of this paper is based on the Theories of Acculturation, Cultural Imperialism and Modernization. Schumann the proponent of the acculturation theory explained it as the degree people adapts or acculturates to a new cultural group Schumann (1978 as cited in Mac-Moses, 2015:18). His view is that language or clothing will control the degree to which people acquires the foreign culture, and that when two culture meets, there are bound to be adaptations on both sides, though the minority culture will adhere to most of these changes, during this acculturation process. He advocates there will be some significant aspects of the indigenous cultural traditions that would be lost due to the influence of the superior culture. This is so especially that student who tries to maintain their indigenous fashionable dressing in social environment that is dominated by foreign fashion may feel alienated from the rest (Berry, 2008 as cited in Mac-Moses, 2015:19). The implication of all of this could lead to poor self-esteem among other social difficulties. Ward (2001) noted however that people or society change, by copying from situation induced by the encounter with an unfamiliar circumstance, on the part of individuals to learn and acquire specific cultural skills to thrive in a certain cultural space.

Another theory related to this paper is the Theory of Cultural Imperialism propounded by Schiller (1973). Cultural imperialism theorists argued that the media and fashion industries are the products of western cultural civilization, and opines that the rest of the globe purchases these fashions through international trade as the driver of interdependence. The view is that developing countries are watching the foreign media and fashions as well as the ways of dressing, they tends to be driven towards the new ways by destroying their indigenous cultural ways (Egwim, 2010). What is crucial to the theorists is that Africans especially Nigerian university students' do not have the free will to choose how they feel (Adias Raimi & Adia, 2020), think and live; they react to what they see on the media because there is nothing else to compare to it. Hence, as long as the Nigerian students continue to copy foreign fashions more than those Nigerian fashions, they would always believe they should dress, think and live westernized.

The third theory underpinning this paper is modernization theory as propounded by the German sociologist Marx Weber (1864-1920). The anchorage of this theory is digestion of the process of modernization within human societies; it applies a model of a progressive transition from pre-modern to modern society (Raimi & Ekpenyong, 2011). The theory both attempt to identify the social variables that impels social progress and development of societies and seeks to explain the process of social change. This is that it stresses not only the process of change but also the responses to that change and realization of the dynamics while addressing social and cultural structures for the adaptation of new technologies. Modernization theory avers societies tend to develop as they adopt modern ideas as citizens are freer to enjoy a higher standard of living. Development such as modern technology, communication, and production the theorists argued, make modernization a necessity.

The crux of this theoretical flagship is the quest to erode almost all the indigenous values either good or bad that expresses through processes of globalization, as the primary concerns for modernity. The effect of trendsetting dresses on Nigerian students factored in this paper is linked to the three-tiered theoretical analysis of adaptation of foreign fashions. The expression is often attributed to transformation in dressing styles for the

acculturation, cultural imperialism and modernization of the Nigerian students through the mass media, internet and so on. These avenues lead to the adaptation of “foreign fashion” or “westernize” dresses at the detriment of indigenous dresses.

Globalization and Fashion Trends

Dressing is a very important aspect of the human culture, and defines people's ethnic identity. The pattern of dress people wears is a characterization of their norms, values, weather, and resources obtainable in their geographical location as well as expression of modesty (Aishwariya, 2019:270). A dress tells one's social status and role in the society and it gives information about the cultural group that an individual belongs to (Obeta & Uwah, 2015; Twig as cited in Birhan, 2019), and communicates age, gender, occupation, ethnicity, power and religious commitment. Unlike the past, however, contemporary young peoples have been on the march of fashion especially that of dressing and haircuts leaving aside their indigenous values (Amankwah, Howard & Sarpong, 2012). Though there is no universal standard of dressing, dresses are a function of some essential purposes, in all ramifications, whether in the east or west (Imoh as cited in Akpan, 2018), as there are different patterns of dressing; however, there are certain patterns that are considered unacceptable in society. There is always two sides to a coin such that, improper dressing has become major moral misnomer in Nigerian universities that deviates from the normal sociocultural standard, and which affects the value system of the social environment (Birhan, 2019). While the Nigerian sense of decent dressing is part and parcel of life, because it elicits respect and protect the African personality. There is the generally accepted way of dressing without exposing vital parts of the body considered morally essential as standard way of dressing (Ewulo, 2016), Adding that decent dressing creates a sense of attraction for favorable remarks from other people as well as self-respect.

Globalization has changed all of this to somewhat improper dressing and provocative way of dressing relative to the society or culture of the Nigerian students. Adding that this pattern of dressing is provocative, improper and morally unacceptable (Olori as cited in Fareo & Jackson, 2018). These trendsetting dresses as a result of globalization do not conform to the acceptable moral standard of decent dressing in Nigeria. This is so as students' dresses to show off parts of the body such as the breast, buttocks, or even pants that ought to be covered. Hence, these dresses expose vital parts of the body to the public, deliberately flaunting it everywhere. This dressing practice is contrary to the acceptable norms and values of society (Yohanna, Sababa & Filgona, 2020:32), that are not appropriate for a particular situation. The implication is that these dress styles are morally offensive and reveal the high rate of moral decadence in the Nigerian society of our time.

Although there are a number of empirical studies on the consequences of these dresses as the results vary, but the consistent observable dressing mode is disruptive and distractive. As Akpan (cited in Yohanna, Sababa & Filgona, 2020:32) among others “trousers and skirts worn below the waist (sagging), singlet, spaghetti blouse, low neck blouse exposing the breasts, skirts with a slit above the knees, transparent dresses, shirts and blouses...chains, tattoo with provocative writing or picture, and noisy shoe heels.” Whatever someone else interpretation may be, the dressing pattern does not conform to the norms and values of the Nigerian society. But of great importance is “dress to kill” as it

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is called on campuses is rampant among university students (oral interview with Mike Gowon 2/2/2022). All in the name of fashion and desire to look sexy, tantalizing, sweet, and happening babies on campuses (oral interview with Theresa Thompson 8/2/2022), smarting under the disguise of fashionable dresses are major moral challenges associated with decency in dressing observed in our universities today.

Besides the skimpiness and tight-fitting nature of these dresses, they are again transparent; revealing certain parts of the bodies that under normal and acceptable dress pattern ought to be hidden away from the glare of the public. The story of male students is as ugly as those of female ones, for they have been subjected to arrest with hooligans because of improper dressing. In the current dispensation, male students have fixed hairs, pierce ears, thereby making them look like notorious criminals while their female counterparts become victims of rape, sexual harassment and other vices (oral interview with Jessica Adebayo 23/3/2022). This unfortunate social problem has spread into all the fabrics of not only tertiary institutions but also the Nigerian society at large. Stated differently, universities are now established centers of this improper dressing galore to the point of it becoming the new normal trendsetting fashionable (oral interview with Gift Zacchaes 28/3/2022).

Certainly the way one dresses showcases what stuff he/she is made off, whether the person is responsible or not. As the popular saying goes “you dress in the way that you will be addressed”. As Rykrsmith (cited in Ojogbane, Amonjenu&Husseini2020) opined that what you wear affects others’ perceptions of you. This is saying that the type of dress one wears communicates symbolically about his/her social identity. It is therefore necessary to dress in the image one wants to portray oneself. The expression is that dressing in a manner in which religion and other social institutions as well as society frowns at is certainly not civilization; it is antithetical to Nigeria’s cultural value system. This is because such behaviors were only attributed to destitute in society. However, this is now very popular among students in Nigeria’s higher institutions of learning (oral interview with Aisha Usman 26/3/2022).

The proliferation of this cankerworm among students is as a result of the perception of uniqueness, a symbol of being campus queens, happening babies as well as big boys (oral interview with Ibrahim Shehu 23/1/2022). He adds further that the consequences of foreign fashions on students are becoming victims of rape on campuses, lured to prostitution by peer group influence as well as being cultists. It implies that overexposure to foreign fashions through mass media, internet, films, and music videos has been instrumental on the moral decadence of students, especially those at the tertiary levels. Dresses that are meant for stage costumes for musicians were mistaken by students as normal wears in these institutions. As Ahmed (cited in Akpan, 2018) suggests, if one really dresses to kill, one could not help but marvel at the number of students that must have been “dying morally” in these universities as a result of this trendsetting fashion revolution.

Like other revolutions various factors were considered to have contributed to trendsetting fashion among students in Nigerian universities. What impels contemporary fashion is associated with low self-esteem and perception the push factor (female and male) showcases the wrong fashion especially by female undergraduates to attract attention. Eijeden (2010) noted that, the family background of the person plays a

significant role in the dressing pattern of a child while others subscribes that the mass media and the issue of modeling is the major influence of the fashion revolution among young people. But one informant adds to this list, the environment, peer group pressure, the negative influence of the internet, and changing social values, poor parenting (oral interview with Ota Eferebo 12/1/2022), are some factors taken into consideration. While Chukwudi and Gbakorumi (2011) extended the spread of the menace to some biological changes experienced by both sexes as they grow. The complexity of fashion trend is difficult to comprehend as another interviewee widen the scope to fading values, foreign influence, social media, covetousness, entertainment and fashion industries as well as demonic influence (oral interview with Judith Gowon 18/4/2022).

Following the widespread trendsetting dresses among university students, which have attracted tremendous efforts by the management of institutions to curb its excesses. One such effort according to one interviewee was the introduction of dress code and strict rules enforcing compliance of students in many tertiary institutions. She went further to say that, at the Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria, and management enforces dress code right at the gate in which case students are screened before they venture into the university premises. Those wearing dresses that are incongruent with the dress code are sent back home and change to decent dresses as approved by the institution's management for good behavior or conduct as long as he/she wishes to be a student. Adding that there are exceptional cases when those that leaves on campus messes with the dress code they are quickly sent out of the classes after serious warning for that bad behavior (oral interview with Chidiebere Okeke 22/9/2021). She disclosed further that as a member of the dress code committee at the Faculty of Humanities representing History Department of the institution, as her constituent, is to see to the full compliance of the dress code by all students.

This is so as education is basically aimed at the development of the total personality of students and inculcates positive values in their behavioral attitudes. The attainment of these laudable goals of education cannot be realized unless something is done to curb all these distractive measures and creates conducive environment for effective teaching and learning; as universities are not fashion galore. Discipline is an essential ingredient of education as oxygen is to life. The attitudes and values students constitute the critical factor in the level of discipline in education. There is therefore need for students to be aided in clarifying their values and modifying their attitudes to be able to make rational decisions in a socially, acceptable way (Nwagwu cited in Ojogbane, Amonjenu&Husseini, 2020:34), for positive change.

The worry is that even though these dresses are not accepted as the normality, is seen to be gaining more grounds. One then wonders what becomes of the society in future about the number of students that are being graduated from these institutions. This is as the Nigerian social environment is a moral community that must be preserved. Therefore, the dress code adaptation by the various institutions management should be maintained with sheer determination for good. As many empirical studies have diagnose the impact of trendsetting fashion on students' academic success though the findings are conflicting and inconsistent. Akpan (2018) investigation found among others contributes to poor academic performance as it makes the students a target of many lecturers for sexual gratification, which on refusal may result in failure and victimization, one example. While Whitehurst (as

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cited in Oluwadare, Otunaiya & Opeoluwa, 2020) showed that there is no significant relationship between fashionable dressing and academic performance of female undergraduate students. This implies that students who engage in fashionable dresses still perform well academically, another example. Amidst growing concerns expressed in many quarters about the proliferation of foreign fashionable dressing especially females indicates that students' were not affected alone, but also the larger society ostensibly to entice the opposite sex.

Effect of Foreign Fashion on Students Dressing

The effect of foreign fashion on students dressing has a plethora of scholarly literature such as Egwim (2010), Adams and Macpherson (2013), Akpan (2018), Ojogbane, Amonjenu & Hussein (2020) for examples. However, empirical studies have shown that it can affect the students negatively, and argued further that students conduct and performances are related to his/her dressing pattern. Therefore, university authorities are more concerned with the students' dressing; this is because a student dressing should not be a distraction to teaching/learning environment. Unfortunately, students often dress in foreign seductive fashion that tends to distract lecturers as well as course mates from task of learning. It certainly disrupts classes, putting the lecturer to the task of effective classroom management skills, thereby challenging the potential teaching/learning condition into one of chaos.

Foreign fashionable clothes promote improper dressing. Okoh (2010) contend that these fashionable dresses have come to characterize the dress pattern of many students, especially the female ones that wears funny dresses as new normal to show off parts of the body such as breasts, buttocks and so on. There are those who believe that foreign fashion is as a result of demonic influence and immorality. Accordingly, this form of dressing as a result of foreign fashion is provocative and morally unacceptable to the Nigerian society. It also portrays the degree of moral decadence that has eaten into body politic of our society. Empirical studies have revealed that dressing seductive in these dresses by students have the tendency of impacting negatively on the academic performance (Akperi & Raimi, 2016) as well as the output of male lecturers most especially when they concentrate on watching those provocative dressing during lecture hours (oral interview with Agnes Lawson 4/5/2022). She adds that female students spend a lot of money purchasing these dresses instead of spending it on academic materials, rather, as a way of making money to be exclusive students on campus they patronize night clubs, brothels and hotels where they can have fun at expense of their studies.

There is hardly any higher institution of learning in the country that is not challenged with the adverse effect of foreign fashions on the students dressing styles. The way the female undergraduates dresses also leaves much to be desired. What the girls call skirts that they wear is just "one inch" longer than their pants. Such foreign fashionable clothes are the preference of students that attracts many vices, ranges from rape, prostitution, sexual harassment and the inability of these students to complete their academic programs (oral interview with Eunice Ateki 12/2/2022). It therefore stressed those foreign dresses worn by students on campuses shows off parts of the body. This

exposure is deliberately done in order to look sensuous, fantasizing and tantalizing so as to attract the attention of the opposite sex (Gbadegbe & Quashie, 2013:166).

Certainly poor parenting, peer pressure, societal preference for foreign dresses, wrong use of the internet, fading values, media, among others are some of the motivating factors that influence students to dress seductively in these foreign fashions. Universities are citadel of learning for the development of sound moral behavior, as well as builders of society has been questioned. However, students have departed from their indigenous fashions due to foreign influence. They are only concerned on how to look good, sexy and attractive. Several of these male students in order to be flashy ended up as cultists, kidnapers, armed robbers, drug peddlers and so on. Whereas the female ones are known for prostitution, child trafficking, drug carriers, among others.

V. Conclusion

Based on the finding of this study, it was concluded that Nigeria's public universities have taken so many processes of fashion circles by students to evolve into trendsetting dresses that is viewed as unethical, corrupt and eroding modesty of the African reality. The ideals of decent dressing as a medium of protecting the essential parts of the body, environmental conditions and being expression of status, occupation, age and gender has been seriously threatened in Nigeria's public universities, as centers of trendsetting fashions. Although arising from social changes of the value system through lens of globalization, it was observed that students' negative attitudes and perception towards dressing decently is becoming an incurable cancer that need to be cured. This is especially that the perception of the students should be considered to know the best approach that can be applied to curb this menace in the system as well as counseling, parents, university management and the larger society have a significant role to play in downplaying this menace that has eaten deep into the fabrics of public universities in Nigeria.

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